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H-2', H-5', H-6'), 6.78 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.52 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 5.42 (1H, dd, J 9, 2 Hz, H-2), 2.80 (2H, m, two H-3) and 2.30 (12H, br, 4 phenolic acetoxy). It was identified as (-) eriodictyol and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. It is the first report of its isolation from this genus.

Compound B: Elutions with 10% EtOAc in C_6H_6 afforded this compound and it was crystallised from EtOAc- C_6H_6 (120 mg), m.p. 327-29°; gave brown colour with ferric chloride and pink colour with Mg/HCl; ν_{max} (KBr) 1650 (CO) and 3300 cm^{-1} (OH); acetate δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.60 (2H, br, H-2', H-6'), 7.20 (3H, br, H-5', H-3, H-8), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6) and 2.25 (12H, s, 4 phenolic acetoxy). These data suggest compound B to be luteolin and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. This is the first report of its isolation from this genus.

Compound C: It was obtained from elutions with 10% EtOAc in C_6H_6 and crystallised from EtOAc- C_6H_6 (2 g), m.p. 238-40°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ (MeOH); colour reactions suggested a flavonoid skeleton; ν_{max} (KBr) 1620 (CO) and 3350 cm^{-1} (OH); acetate δ ($CdCl_2$) 7.20 (3H, m, H-2', H-5', H-6'), 6.72 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.52 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 5.60 (1H, d, J 12 Hz, H-2), 5.35 (1H, d, J 12 Hz, H-3), 2.21 (12H, s, 4 phenolic acetoxy) and 1.98 (3H, s, aliphatic acetoxy). These data suggest compound C to be dihydroquercetin and the identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Dihydroquercetin has already been reported² in *Pistacia chinensis*.

Chemical Components of *Pistacia integerrima*

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PISTACIA integerrima (Anacardiaceae) is available at Solan, Himachal Pradesh. Its galls, formed on its leaves, by hemipteris, have been reported¹ to have medicinal values against cough, fever, loss of appetite, nose bleeding, vomiting and stomach troubles. Since *P. integerrima* has not been subjected to chemical examination earlier, we have investigated its heartwood obtained from Solan. The plant material (2 kg) was chopped into small pieces and then extracted with hot ethanol. The extractives were column chromatographed over silica gel and three compounds labelled as A, B and C could be isolated and characterised.

Compound A: It was obtained from elutions with 5% EtOAc in C_6H_6 and crystallised from EtOAc- C_6H_6 (100 mg), m.p. 270-72°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ (MeOH); colour reactions indicated flavonoid skeleton; ν_{max} (KBr) 1620 (CO) and 3300 cm^{-1} (OH); acetate (Ac_2O/Py) δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.25 (3H, br,

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